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Research Article

**RISK OF PNEUMONIA IN CHRONIC LUNG DISEASE AMONG
LOCAL POPULATION OF PAKISTAN****Dr. Sobia Abbas¹, Dr Balaj Hassan², Dr Maha Arshad³**¹District Headquarters Hospital Vehari, ²FCPS Medicine and Allied Health Sciences, ³Lahore Medical and Dental College.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Despite the fact that free vaccination is available in Pakistan, pneumonia is killing around 92,000 children annually under-five years of age, health experts said Tuesday during a press briefing to mark upcoming World Pneumonia Day on November 12.

Objective: The main objective of the study is to analyze the risk of pneumonia in chronic lung disease among local population of Pakistan.

Methodology of the study: This study was conducted at District Hospital Vehari during January 2019 to June 2019. This study was done with the permission of ethical committee. For this purpose we select 50 patients of pneumonia for further analysis. The patients of both gender were selected for this study.

Result: Significant differences were observed between patients who received extra-fine versus fine-particle COPD in the demographics and baseline characteristics, as shown in Table 1. The COPD treatments prescribed to patients before and at step-up are shown in S1 Table in the supporting information.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the COPD exacerbation rate was higher among the patients who had a history of pneumonia or a high rate of COPD exacerbation in the preceding period of 1 year.

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INTRODUCTION:

Despite the fact that free vaccination is available in Pakistan, pneumonia is killing around 92,000 children annually under-five years of age, health experts said Tuesday during a press briefing to mark upcoming World Pneumonia Day on November 12. Inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) are widely used in high doses in the management of obstructive lung diseases such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Current asthma treatment guidelines recommend stepping up the ICS dose if lack of control persists. Alternatively, the combination of low-dose ICS with long-acting β 2-agonist (LABA) has been shown to achieve better asthma control, sparing patients higher doses of ICS [1]. In patients with COPD, low-dose ICS/LABA combination has been shown to reduce exacerbations, improve quality of life and lung function, through an underlying complementary anti-inflammatory cellular action. However there continues to be significant concern regarding inappropriate prescribing of high-dose ICS in patients with obstructive lung diseases, with untoward consequences for patients [2].

The first laboratory based observational study was conducted in Rawalpindi between 2002 and 2003. The study demonstrates a low diagnostic yield for isolated pathogens 88 out of 510 specimens (17.25%). Most commonly identified pathogen was *Haemophilus influenzae* (HI) with a strikingly high relative frequency (64 out of 88) among isolates³. However, this yield is reported in a majority of paediatric population (41 out of 64) with 33 being less than five years of age. These figures therefore will not be in any way reflective of adult CAP status.

Indeed, regular use of ICS has been linked to several systemic effects, including a higher risk of pneumonia, where it is thought that ICS exert an anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effect that could affect the pathogenesis of pneumonia [3]. Most randomized controlled trials (RCTs), observational studies and meta-analysis, in patients with COPD suggest an increased risk of pneumonia with a dose-response relationship between ICS and pneumonia, although there is some evidence suggesting to the contrary [4]. This association is not as clear-cut in asthmatics; ICS are associated with a decreased risk of pneumonia based on RCTs, but observational studies suggest a higher risk of pneumonia⁵. Importantly though, all the published literature has assessed the risk of pneumonia only for conventional fine-particle ICS and not for

extra-fine particle ICS in patients with obstructive lung disease.

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates, pneumonia accounts for 16 percent of the total child deaths making it the leading killer of children less than 5 years of age globally. Pneumonia is a form acute respiratory infection that affects lungs. When an individual has pneumonia, the alveoli (small sacs in lungs which fill with air when a healthy person breathes) are filled with pus and fluid, which makes breathing painful and limits oxygen intake. It is to be noted that vaccines are considered second only to clean drinking water in reducing infectious diseases, he added. Pneumonia is caused by a number of infectious agents, including viruses, bacteria and fungi. The most common causes of pneumonia amongst children include *streptococcus pneumoniae* and *haemophilus influenzae* type b (Hib) [6].

Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study is to analyze the risk of pneumonia in chronic lung disease among local population of Pakistan.

Methodology of the study:

This study was conducted at District Hospital Vehari during January 2019 to June 2019. This study was done with the permission of ethical committee. For this purpose we select 50 patients of pneumonia for further analysis. The patients of both gender were selected for this study. Diagnosis of pneumonia: (i) unconfirmed i.e. all unique patients with codes for pneumonia and, (ii) confirmed by chest radiograph or resulting in hospitalization within one month of pneumonia diagnosis.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients with any other chronic respiratory disease, at any time were excluded from the study.

Statistical analyses:

The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 19. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULT:

Significant differences were observed between patients who received extra-fine versus fine-particle COPD in the demographics and baseline characteristics, as shown in Table 1. The COPD treatments prescribed to patients before and at step-up are shown in S1 Table in the supporting information.

Table 01: Baseline and clinical characteristics of pneumonia patients with obstructive lung diseases

Demographic and clinical baseline characteristics		COPD		P-value ^a
		Patients (n = 50)		
		Fine-particle	Extra-fine particle	
Demographics				
Sex, female		9046 (61)	4871 (59)	0.004
Age		44 (17)	44 (18)	0.018
Baseline weight BMI (kg/m ²), mean (SD)		28 (7)	29 (7)	0.001
Smoking ^b	Non-smokers	8679 (59)	4873 (59)	0.024
	Current smokers	3474 (24)	1904 (23)	
	Ex-smokers	2476 (17)	1392 (17)	
Respiratory diagnosis	None	174 (1.2)	114 (1.4)	NA
	Asthma/ no COPD	11516 (77.9)	7171 (87.2)	
	COPD/ no asthma	197 (1.3)	93 (1.1)	
	Asthma and COPD	2901 (19.6)	847 (10.3)	
Comorbidities and Therapy				
Rhinitis diagnosis and/or therapy ^c		6175 (42)	2754 (34)	<0.001
GERD diagnosis and/or drugs ^d		3827 (26)	2115 (26)	0.784
Ischaemic heart disease diagnosis ^e		1084 (7)	433 (5)	<0.001
Coding for pneumonia ^f		73 (0.5)	22 (0.3)	0.010
Confirmed coding for pneumonia ^g		25 (0.2)	12 (0.1)	0.674
Baseline characteristics				
Acute oral corticosteroid courses ^h	0	8542 (58)	6008 (73)	<0.001
	1	3103 (21)	1420 (17)	
	2+	3143 (21)	797 (10)	
Antibiotics prescribed with lower respiratory consultation ⁱ	0	9027 (61)	5440 (66)	<0.001
	1	3060 (21)	1667 (20)	
	2+	2701 (18)	118 (14)	

DISCUSSION:

The pathophysiological mechanisms that contribute to an increased susceptibility to pneumonia in patients treated with ICS are unclear. In murine models, ICS have been shown to significantly increase alveolar macrophage efferocytosis (uptake of apoptotic cells by alveolar macrophages), thereby reducing their ability to combat microbes [7], including *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, the most common cause of community acquired pneumonia in patients with COPD [8]. A recent study in a cohort of children with persistent asthma taking daily ICS showed nearly four times greater oropharyngeal colonization with *Streptococcus pneumoniae* compared to children not receiving ICS, which may increase the risk of having pneumococcal respiratory infections. Several studies have demonstrated an intra-class difference between both mono-component ICS and fixed combinations of ICS/LABA with regard to the risk of pneumonia and pneumonia related events in COPD patients [9-10]. The risk of patients with COPD

developing serious pneumonia is particularly elevated and dose related with fluticasone use and much lower with budesonide. Although there have been no studies directly comparing the effects of fluticasone and budesonide on host defence, differences are likely related to their contrasting pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties. To prevent any confounding by differences between FP and budesonide, we therefore excluded patients using budesonide in our current analyses [11].

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the COPD exacerbation rate was higher among the patients who had a history of pneumonia or a high rate of COPD exacerbation in the preceding period of 1 year.

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